

Assessing students' attributes expressed through a school life formula

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Abstract

St. Dominic College of Asia's school life's formula embodies the aspirations of an institution when it comes to quality academics and support services, which are basically part and parcel of its quality policy. This research used descriptive, survey design of quantitative research. The total sample for this research was 1,243 students from first to fourth year who were given researcher-made Likert-type questionnaire that was validated and was found reliable at $\alpha=.921$. The study showed that majority of life formula indicators (10 out of 11) were assessed between means of 3.61 to 4.09, which is 'very often,' whereas collaboration and community engagement only had an overall rating of 'often.' The institution should expose the students to a learning environment and community that could give the opportunity to experience meeting the expectations set in SDCA School Life Formula by the outcomes-based education (OBE) approach.

Keywords: Students; attributes; St. Dominic College of Asia; school life formula.

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Introduction

St. Dominic College of Asia's school life's formula embodies the aspirations of an institution when it comes to quality academics and support services, which are basically part and parcel of its quality policy (Adanza, 2016). The following statistical results are part of a bigger study to assess how the students achieved the life formula and eventually academic excellence. The components are the following: Research and product development, multicultural advocacy, moral and spiritual accountability, understanding the discipline, self-directed learning, information and technology literacy, communication skills, creativity and innovation, collaboration and community engagement, critical thinking, and engagement with the community (Ana & Adanza, 2021).

For this institution to determine whether the students meet the expectations set before them through the quality policy as expressed through the Life Formula, a survey was conducted. The survey was about students' views about how the institutional outcomes / expected attributes are able to help or develop knowledge, skills, and attitude. Having these attributes may suggest that indeed SDCA is truthful to its quality policy which is anchored on quality academics and support services.

Methodology

This research used descriptive, survey design of quantitative research. The total sample for this research was 1,243 students from first to fourth year who were given researcher-made Likert-type questionnaire that was validated and was found reliable at $\alpha=.921$. The data gathering was done online through Google Forms. The highest point is 5 and the lowest is 1. Statistical analysis was done through weighted mean to determine the level of attributes of students as expressed through the school life formula.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 observed that almost all of the statements in the research and product development were rated 'very often', with majority of the students believed that this outcome is important (Mean = 4.10). It can be noticed that the item 12 "I have been assigned to write a paper, report, or writing task from 11 pages or more" had a rating of 'often' (Mean = 3.23), which can be enhanced further when writing a research paper or report. Despite this, students can easily practice the learned language skills like in researching a topic or writing a paper by exposure to real-world situations (Milad, 2017).

Table 1. Research and product development

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I demonstrate the ability to develop research and to produce scientific and entrepreneurial outputs.	3.74	Very often
2	I prepare to give a proper presentation.	3.96	Very often
3	I work independently.	3.85	Very often
4	I conduct surveys to study on a topic.	3.68	Very often
5	I use varied resource materials in my research.	3.95	Very often
6	I reach conclusions based on my own analysis of numerical information (e.g., numbers, graphs, statistics)	3.73	Very often
7	I use numerical information to examine a real-world problem or issue (e.g., unemployment, climate change)	3.58	Very often
8	I evaluate what others have concluded from numerical information.	3.66	Very often
9	I work while upholding intellectual honesty by avoiding plagiarism.	3.95	Very often
10	I have been assigned to write a paper, report, or writing task up to 5 pages.	3.61	Very often
11	I have been assigned to write a paper, report, or writing task between 6 and 10 pages.	3.42	Very often
12	I have been assigned to write a paper, report, or writing task from 11 pages or more.	3.23	Often
13	I have done or plan to do this before I graduate: To work with a faculty member on a research project.	3.42	Very often
14	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.10	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 2 indicated that all of the statements in the multicultural advocacy were rated 'very often', with majority of the students believed that this outcome is important (Mean = 4.08). It also implies that most students have earned and learned a sense of respect towards colleagues regardless of their racial or cultural differences. Civitillo et al. (2017) highlighted the importance of understanding of cultural diversity approaches at school among teachers and students by fostering equality and promoting cultural pluralism.

Table 2. Multicultural advocacy

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I demonstrate knowledge, values, and beliefs of various cultures.	4.06	Very often
2	I effectively engage in a multicultural society.	3.81	Very often
3	I interact with others and develop a different view about traditions.	3.94	Very often
4	I connect learning to societal problems or issues.	3.78	Very often
5	I try to better understand someone else's views by imagining how an issue looks from his or her perspective.	3.95	Very often
6	I include diverse perspectives (e.g., political, racial / ethnic, gender) in course discussions or assignments.	3.76	Very often
7	I respect people with different race or ethnicity.	3.65	Very often
8	I respect people from an economic background other than my own.	3.69	Very often
9	I understand and communicate among students from different backgrounds (e.g., social, racial / ethnic, religious).	3.91	Very often
10	I attend events that address important social, economic, or political issues.	3.70	Very often
11	I respond positively to racial, ethnic, cultural, and language differences.	3.81	Very often
12	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.08	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 3. Moral and spiritual accountability

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I embrace moral or spiritual values in living one's life (e.g., being honest, loyal, respectful).	4.06	Very often
2	I apply moral or spiritual values to all aspects of life.	3.81	Very often
3	Teachers and staff members provide me a support for overall well-being (e.g., recreation, health care, counseling).	3.94	Very often
4	Teachers and staff members provide me an assistance in non-academic responsibilities.	3.78	Very often
5	I am a responsible, informed, and active citizen of the country.	3.95	Very often
6	I have developed or clarified a personal code of values and ethics.	3.76	Very often
7	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.08	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 3 showed that most students have 'very often' to 'always' ratings in the following statements of moral and spiritual accountability. It also reveals that most students have embraced moral or spiritual values in living one's life, which got a mean of 4.29. This study confirms the findings of Baring (2018) which mentions a personal sense of religiosity, an institutional / communal view of spirituality, and an ethical spiritual sense acquired by the students.

Table 4. Understanding the discipline

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I demonstrate a deeper and meaningful understanding of coursework.	4.03	Very often
2	I examine the strengths of my own views on a topic or issue.	4.06	Very often
3	I examine the weaknesses of my own views on a topic or issue.	3.99	Very often
4	I memorize course materials.	3.89	Very often
5	I apply facts, theories, or methods to practical problems or new situations.	3.92	Very often
6	I analyze an idea, experience, or line of reasoning in depth by examining its parts.	3.97	Very often
7	I apply necessary skills aligned with the industry / professional standards.	3.95	Very often
8	I participate in an internship, field experience, student teaching, or clinical placement.	4.01	Very often
9	I participate in an international exposure / immersion program.	3.83	Very often
10	I complete academic requirements (e.g., capstone course, thesis, feasibility).	4.10	Very often
11	I participate in an in-/off-campus competition.	3.69	Very often
12	I acquire assessment and certification.	3.96	Very often
13	I participate in culminating activities.	3.89	Very often
14	I spend significant amount of time studying and on academic work.	3.97	Very often
15	I know that teachers provide support to help students succeed academically.	3.96	Very often
16	I prepare for a class.	3.09	Often
17	I study, read, and write.	3.19	Often
18	I do homework.	3.06	Often
19	I analyze data.	3.11	Often
20	I rehearse in other academic activities.	3.11	Often
21	I participate in co-curricular activities (organizations, campus publications, student government, intercollegiate or intramural sports).	3.09	Often
22	I acquire job or work-related competencies.	3.78	Very often
23	I develop soft skills (e.g., interpersonal relationship, group work, collaboration, cooperation).	3.93	Very often
24	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.18	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 4 revealed that majority of the students have 'often' to 'very often' ratings in the following statements in understanding the discipline. It also reveals that most students believed that this outcome is important, with a mean of 4.18. This table shows that students have truly managed their behavior and practice that can be observed at school. This result further suggested an improved student discipline which was accomplished by the students (Mack & Reyes-Chua, 2019).

Table 5. Self-directed learning

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I embrace moral or spiritual values in living one's life (e.g., being honest, loyal, respectful).	4.04	Very often
2	I apply moral or spiritual values to all aspects of life.	3.72	Very often
3	Teachers and staff members provide me a support for overall well-being (e.g., recreation, health care, counseling).	3.75	Very often
4	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.24	Always

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 5 showed that most students have rated 'very often' in almost all of the statements in self-directed learning, whereas item 4 "I believe that this outcome is important" had the highest rating provided by the students which has an interpretation of 'always.' This result implies that students really learn to work independently while completing a task. According to Tekkol and Demirel (2018), students are thought to be highly motivated, have an intent on self-improvement, and determined to continue their education.

Table 6. Information and technology literacy

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I access variety of IT sources and materials.	3.61	Very often
2	I use variety of IT sources and materials.	3.60	Very often
3	I evaluate variety of IT sources and materials.	3.58	Very often
4	I produce variety of IT sources and materials (e.g., Office application, graphic design, multimedia).	3.45	Very often
5	I use learning support services.	3.75	Very often
6	I use library services.	3.77	Very often
7	I use laboratories.	3.58	Very often
8	I use computer rooms.	3.54	Very often
9	I use digital and information technology academy application.	3.67	Very often
10	I use other applications (e.g., Autocad, Adobe).	3.48	Very often
11	I use Microsoft Office 365 (e.g., Excel, PowerPoint, Word).	3.72	Very often
12	My experience in Digital Campus at SDCA contributed to my knowledge and skills development.	3.60	Very often
13	I believe that this outcome is important.	3.98	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 6 indicated that most students rated ‘very often’ in all of the statements in the information and technology literacy. This shows that most students believed that this outcome is important (Mean = 3.98). This result highlights that students have acquired computer skills and literacy through using information technology. It also supported the study of Siddiq et al. (2017) which suggested the implementation of a novel assessment for determining students’ 21st century skills, such as digital information, real-time student-student communication, collaboration, and problem solving skills.

Table 7. Communication skills

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I communicate effectively and confidently for many different audiences.	3.79	Very often
2	I ask questions or contribute to course discussion in other ways.	3.74	Very often
3	I explain course material to one or more students.	3.71	Very often
4	I do individual or group performances to explore and express ideas, thoughts, feelings, values, and understanding.	3.89	Very often
5	I speak articulately and use media to communicate effectively.	3.75	Very often
6	I listen actively to the intent and spirit of other words and respond appropriately.	3.81	Very often
7	I comprehend a range of written, spoken, and visual text to convey information.	3.81	Very often
8	I write clearly and effectively.	3.82	Very often
9	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.04	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 7 appeared that most students rated ‘very often’ in all of the statements in the communication skills. It shows that most students believed that this outcome is important (Mean = 4.04). This proves that effective communication skills help students to join clear conversations with their colleagues, both in written and oral forms. Li et al. (2017) considered some educational activities to be taught to the students such as interactive educational modules on teaching skills for communication and decision-making.

Table 8. Creativity and innovation

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I demonstrate the ability to work creatively in any setting that result in a productive output.	3.91	Very often
2	I attend an art exhibit, play, or other arts performance (e.g., dance, theater, music).	3.58	Very often
3	I connect ideas from my course to my prior experiences and knowledge.	3.82	Very often
4	My institution emphasizes attending to campus activities and events such as performing arts and athletic events.	3.82	Very often
5	I believe that this outcome is important.	4.04	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 8 pointed that most students rated ‘very often’ in all of the statements in the creativity and innovation. It is revealed that majority of the students believed that this outcome is important (Mean = 4.04). This signals that students learned to come up with new ideas and approaches when doing an output based on their real-life experiences. It is no doubt that creativity has a role in problem solving, therefore students understand why simple procedures work effectively and apply to different situations in the real world (Cropley, 2015).

Table 9. Collaboration and community engagement

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I demonstrate responsible participation in community-related activities.	3.82	Very often
2	I work with other students on course projects or assignments.	3.86	Very often
3	I work effectively with others.	3.84	Very often
4	I work with a faculty member on activities other than course works (committees, student groups).	3.51	Very often
5	I hold a formal leadership role in a student organization or group.	3.55	Very often
6	My institution emphasizes providing opportunities to be involved in community and volunteerism.	3.74	Very often
7	I participate in mangrove planting.	2.58	Sometimes
8	I participate in coastal cleanup.	2.48	Sometimes
9	I participate in tree planting.	2.33	Sometimes
10	I participate in Maragondon extension projects (livelihood and literacy).	2.19	Sometimes
11	I participate in fun run.	2.47	Sometimes
12	I participate in gift giving.	2.37	Sometimes
13	I participate in calamity and disaster preparedness programs.	2.30	Sometimes
14	I believe that this outcome is important.	3.43	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 9 revealed that most students rated ‘very often’ in some of the statements in collaboration and community engagement. It is revealed that majority of the students have worked with other students on course projects or assignments with a mean rating of 3.86. However, it is also found that there are low ratings when it comes to participation into different programs (items 7 to 13) or interpreted as ‘sometimes.’ Students are intended to help a school extend a learning community, though participation can be improved for further academic support and wellbeing. It is necessary first to gather and synthesize knowledge from different fields to create an integrated strategy that would better involve the community in sustainability initiatives (Too & Bajracharya, 2015).

Table 10. Critical thinking

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I identify a relevant assumption or implications.	3.80	Very often
2	I evaluate arguments and apply analytic thought to analyze coherent arguments.	3.77	Very often
3	I combine ideas from different courses when completing assignments.	3.77	Very often
4	I learn something that changed the way I understand an issue or concept.	3.85	Very often
5	I evaluate a point of view, decision, or information source.	3.85	Very often
6	I form a new idea or understanding from various pieces of information.	3.82	Very often
7	I think critically and analytically.	3.83	Very often
8	I analyze numerical and statistical information.	3.74	Very often
9	I solve complex real-world problems.	3.77	Very often
10	I use innovative methods and technologies to solve problems and make decisions.	3.77	Very often
11	I respond to multiple experiences and ideas about the world.	3.80	Very often
12	I construct and apply knowledge, concept theories, and generations to make meaning.	3.81	Very often
13	I believe that this outcome is important.	3.99	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 10 revealed that most students have a rating of ‘very often’ in all of the statements in critical thinking. It is shown that majority of the students believed that this outcome is important (Mean = 3.99). It is implied that students learn how to make decisions by themselves. According to Birgili (2015), critical thinking is necessary for the production of technological innovations and long-term educational sustainability, which can be applicable to problem-based learning approach.

In Table 11, results also revealed that most students were very often engaged in almost all of the people in the SDCA community, whereas they are more engaged when they interact with their fellow students (Mean = 3.84). It is also seen that they were only often engaged with the security personnel and the cashier. Despite this, engagement towards people was positive among student respondents. This is similar with the study of Cleofas (2020) that students who participated in more school organizations and had more interactions with school personnel showed higher levels of general positive affect and life satisfaction, while it is important to maintain the linkages between students and other educational institutions as well as their significant peer interactions.

Table 11. Engagement with SDCA community

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Fellow students	3.84	Very often
2	Academic advisers	3.79	Very often
3	Faculty	3.74	Very often
4	Student wellness staff	3.65	Very often
5	Student development staff	3.68	Very often
6	Athletics and cultural staff	3.59	Very often
7	Management information system staff	3.56	Very often
8	Health services staff	3.68	Very often
9	Security personnel	3.31	Often
10	Housekeeping personnel	3.60	Very often
11	Accounting staff	3.52	Very often
12	Cashier	3.35	Often
13	Registrar staff	3.49	Very often
14	Library staff	3.70	Very often
15	Others (canteen staff, photocopying staff, business staff)	3.67	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

Table 12. Summary of mean scores of life formula indicators (n=1,243)

Item	Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	Research and Product Development	3.71	Very often
2	Multicultural Advocacy	3.85	Very often
3	Moral and Spiritual Accountability	4.09	Very often
4	Understanding the Discipline	3.77	Very often
5	Self-Directed Learning	3.94	Very often
6	Information and Technology Literacy	3.64	Very often
7	Communication Skills	3.81	Very often
8	Creativity and Innovation	3.84	Very often
9	Collaboration and Community Engagement	3.03	Often
10	Critical Thinking	3.81	Very often
11	Engagement with the SDCA Community	3.61	Very often

Legend: 1.00-1.79: Never; 1.80-2.59: Sometimes; 2.60-3.39: Often; 3.40-4.19: Very often; 4.20-5.00: Always

It can be gleaned from Table 12 that majority of life formula indicators (10 out of 11) were assessed between means of 3.61 to 4.09, which is ‘very often.’ This implies that the students very often meet the competencies required for each indicator. The highest among the indicators or attributes is moral and spiritual accountability (M=4.09). The challenged attribute is collaboration and community engagement at M=3.03 (often). Excellence is also expressed by moral and spiritual accountability as St. Dominic College of Asia does not only want to produce intellectual giants, but also moral and spiritual persons. Moral and spiritual values are emphasized in SDCA alongside with the academics. Furthermore, SDCA wants to produce responsible, informed and active citizens of the country (Ana & Adanza, 2021).

One indicator of academic excellence and eventually quality of life is the capability of the students to find new knowledge and produce new things ($M=3.71$). As early as first year, students are exposed to research in their general education courses, like in English and Filipino subjects. In these subjects they are taught the rudiments of technical and scientific writing and proper citation using the APA format. They are also taught how to develop research, produce scientific and entrepreneurial outputs, present frameworks, conduct surveys, use varied research materials in research, write conclusions based on own analysis of numerical information, use numerical information to examine a real-world problem or issue, evaluate what others have concluded, upholding intellectual honesty, among others.

Multicultural advocacy is also an important aspect of the Life Formula ($M=3.85$). Students are expected to demonstrate knowledge, values, and beliefs of various cultures, effectively engage in a multicultural society, interact with others, and develop a different view about traditions, learn societal problems and issues, among others. Understanding the discipline ($M=3.77$) is one attribute that a Dominican should possess if one wants to exhibit academic excellence. This means a student has a deeper and meaningful understanding of coursework, examines strengths and weaknesses of own views on a topic or issue, memorizes course materials, applies fact, theories, or methods to practical problems or new situations, analyzes ideas, experiences line of reasoning in depth by examining its parts, applies necessary skills aligned with the industry / professional standards, participates in an internship, field internship, field experience, student teaching or clinical placement, international exposures, and immersion programs.

Self-directed learning ($M=3.94$) talks about working independently towards completion of project / activity, review notes before and after the class, and summarizes what learned in class or from course materials. Information and technology literacy ($M=3.64$) is expressed through use and evaluation of variety of IT sources and materials, use of learning support services, libraries, laboratories, and computer rooms. Academic excellence can also be expressed through communication skills ($M=3.81$), which means they can communicate effectively and confidently for many different audiences, ask questions or contribute to course discussion in other ways, explain course material to one or more students, explore and express ideas, thoughts, feelings, values, and understanding, speak articulately by using media to communicate effectively, listen actively to the intent and spirit of others, and comprehend range of written, spoken, and visual text to convey information. Creativity and innovation ($M=3.84$), collaboration and community engagement ($M=3.03$), critical thinking ($M=3.81$), and engagement with the SDCA community ($M=3.61$) are other very important indicators and attributes that may contribute towards academic excellence that the students have tangibly experienced while on their stay at this institution.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The students of SDCA somehow experienced an improved and sustained quality of life and a certain degree of academic excellence as shown by the expectations and attributes embodied in SDCA School Life Formula. However, this institution should never be complacent with the result as it has the capacity to go higher the scale. Higher levels can be achieved provided that the following recommendations can be considered.

The institution should expose the students to a learning environment and community that could give the opportunity to experience meeting the expectations set in SDCA School Life Formula. This could be by adopting the outcomes-based education (OBE) approach of education and other student-centered approaches, having more emphasis on research, accepting more foreign students, and hiring more competent teacher-researchers to strengthen the workforce of the school. A longitudinal study should be conducted related to this topic for five years.

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